

The Effect of Cash Flows on the Share Price on Amman Stock Exchange

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Abstract

This study investigated value relevance of cash flows in ASE, with emphasis on determining whether or not cash flow capture information that influence share prices of the firms listed on ASE. Consequently, the main objective of this research was to investigate and quantify effects of cash flows on the share prices of Jordanian companies. This study found that the cash flows have a statistically-significant effect on the share prices of the Jordanian companies listed on ASE and that the operating cash flows (OCFs), financing cash flows (FCFs), and investment cash flows (ICFs) together explain 13.27% of the variations in these prices. However, whereas the OCFs have positive effect on the share prices of these companies, the effect of FCFs is negative.

Keywords: ASE, Cash flows, financing Cash flows, Investing Cash Flows, Operating Cash Flows.

1. Introduction

Chotkunakitti (2005) mentioned definitions for cash flow accounting, including that it is a financial reporting system that describes the performance of the company in terms of cash. This system is founded on matching of the periodic cash outflows and inflows, free of the credit transactions and the arbitrary accounting allocation. The inflows encompass cash from the trading operations and the long-term finance providers while the outflows encircle the payments for the replacement growth, investment, interest, distributions, and taxation.

The various researchers use any of several classifications of the cash flows. As an example, Bowen, Burgstahler, and Daley (1987) categorized the cash flows into cash flows from operations (OCFs) and cash flows after investment (ICFs). They also categorized them as expected cash flows and unexpected cash flows. However, Clubb (1995) and Chotkunakitti (2005) differentiated the cash flows into OCFs, FCFs, and ICFs, and Clubb (1995) further classified these cash flow categories into expected and unexpected measures.

The cash flows from the investing activities relate to acquisition and the disposal of the productive assets while the cash flows from the financing activities relate to issuance and the repayment of the long-term sources of the capital and the cash flows from the operating activities relate to all the cash flows not defined as financing or investing activities (Richardson et al., 2001).

The CFO is commonly viewed as the most important cash flow category due to that it derives from the firm's main income-producing activities. It gives indication of capacity of the firm to generate cash from its main activities. Besides, the CFOs do basically support the dividends and capital expenditures. If the firm cannot produce cash to pay dividend, repay loans, or make new investments, then it will tend to lend cash from exterior sources, which may result in cash outflows in the future. Some researchers (e.g., Cheng and Hollie (2008)) decomposed the CFOs component of the earnings into cash flows from the cost of the goods sold, cash flows from the sales, cash flows from the operating expenses, and cash flows relating to other expense/revenue items.

The cash available for external financing and investments too reflects the ability of the firm to make new investments and gives the investors an indication of the dividend-paying ability of the company (Chotkunakitti, 2005). Additionally, the CFO is employed in calculating the free cash flow, which is that money earned from the operations after the provision for the capital expenditures at the end of some accounting period. Basically, it is defined as the net cash flow from the operating activities minus the capital expenditures and the dividends on the preferred stock (Lees & Leibman, 2000; Williamson, 2003). In this regard, Mundia (2016) defined the free cash flow as the operating income plus depreciation minus interest expense minus income taxes minus expected loan minus dividends. Dechow and Ge (2006) defined the free cash flow as the cash flows originating from operational activities plus adding the cash flows from financial investments. It is the profits of operation before accounting for the depreciation but after taking into consideration the taxes and dividend payments. According to Mundia (2016), the free cash flow represents the resources which the managers have at their disposal for investment but which could have been distributed among shareholders. High free cash flows should be indicator of increasing or rising stock prices. As regards the effects of cash flows on share prices of companies, it is noticed that earlier research either (i) did not decompose cash flows into their three major elements (investing, operating, and financing cash flows

(ICFs, OCFs, and FCFs, respectively) or (ii) did break the cash flows into these elements but did not investigate the individual effects of all these three elements on share prices of companies. Most of the previous studies concentrated more, or only, on the OCF (e.g., Habib (2010) and Waldron & Jordan (2010)), thus leaving two knowledge gaps in market research. In this regard, the present study addressed these knowledge gaps in two steps: (i) taking into account all three elements of cash flows; and (ii) studying the individual, as well as the combined, effects of these elements on the share prices of companies.

2. Literature review

Novianti et al. (2012) performed a study to explore the effects of changes in cash flow components and accounting profits on stock returns of manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange Market. A sample of 64 manufacturing companies was selected following the purposive sampling approach. The results of multiple linear regression analysis showed that not all independent variables had significant impacts on stock returns. Change in cash flows from investing activities and accounting profits had positive significant effects on stock returns. Meantime, cash flows from operation activities and cash flows from financial activities did not have significant impacts on stock returns.

Hadi et al. (2013) stated that free cash flows are of remarkable importance for external customers and internal members of a firm. The firms having high free cash flows boost their profits by using accruals to balance and naturalize the low profits. This will enhance the firm's market value and ROE. In view of this, Hadi et al. (2013) evaluated the incremental information content of free cash flows so as to describe changes in firm's value and accruals. The research hypotheses were tested using data from sample of 120 companies over a period of six years (beginning of 2005 to end of 2010). The results indicated that there is significant correlation between free cash flows and firm value (or firm size), which they defined as the market price of shares at the end of a period times the number of shares at the end of that period. Additionally, there was a significant, direct relation between firm value and free cash flows at the significance level of 5.0%.

Al Zararee and Al-Azzawi (2014) attempted to investigate the relation between free cash flow to equity (FCFE) and market values of the pharmaceutical sector firms of Jordan by using a valuation methodology taking into account the relations between net income, FCFE, net capital expenditure, debt position, and working capital. The study employed panel data covering the period from 2004 to 2010. Owing to that determination of firm's market value is a difficult issue (taking into consideration many antagonistic factors (e.g., capital expenditure and risk of debt) in the times when the economic environment wherein the firm operates is non-stable), then choice of the particular FCFE equation can influence the firm's market value as much as the profit rate can. The results uncovered that firms' market values can be satisfactorily assessed by FCFE. This result accords with the hypothesis that FCFE has a significant positive influence on the stock market.

Hamza (2014) carried out an investigation in an effort to find answer to the question: Is there relation between the informational content of the statement of cash flows and stock returns of insurance companies listed on the Damascus Securities Exchange Market? The investigation aimed at studying the informational content of the statement of cash flows; studying the nature of the relation between cash flows from operating, investing, and financing activities, each, and stock returns of insurance companies listed on the Damascus Securities Exchange Market; and analyzing and testing the relation between cash flows of the combined activities and stock returns of the insurance companies. Statistically-significant relations, as well as lack of statistically-significant relations, between stock returns and cash flows of the studied companies existed. For certain insurance companies, there were significant positive correlations between stock returns and cash flows from operating and from investing activities while for others the relationships were non-significant. However, no significant relationship between stock returns and cash flows from the three activities combined have been observed for the studied insurance companies. On the other hand, while there were statistically-significant, inverse relations between stock returns and cash flows from financing activities for some companies, associations for others were non-significant.

3. Research Objectives

To determine the effects of cash flows (operating cash flows, financing cash flows, and investing cash flows) on the share prices of Jordanian companies listed on ASE

4. Hypothesis

H2a: Operating cash flows (OCF) have statistically-significant effect on share prices (SP) of companies.

H2b: Investing cash flows (ICF) have statistically-significant effect on share prices (SP) of companies.

H3c: Financing cash flows (FCF) have statistically-significant effect on share prices (SP) of companies.

The foregoing main hypothesis was tested using multiple linear regression analysis according to the following model:

$$SP_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 OCF_{it} + \beta_2 ICF_{it} + \beta_3 FCF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

where

SP: Share price of company i in year t .

α : Intercept

β : Slope

OCFit: Operating cash flows of company i in year t .

ICFit: Investing cash flows of company i in year t .

FCFit: Financing cash flows of company i in year t .

i : Company

t : Current financial year

ε : Model's error of estimate

5. Hypotheses Testing

This section discusses results of the first regression model. The discussion includes the relation between share prices of the sample companies and the cash flows. Table 5.11 displays the results of the robust, fixed-effect GLS regression modeling (that is, according to results of Hausman and Breusch–Pagan Lagrange multiplier tests) using the regression correction with the Driscoll-Kraay standard errors method. The results point that the model fits the data at the 0.01 level of significance. Additionally, in this model the predictors explain 13.27% of the variations in the SPs of the listed companies ($R^2 = 0.1327$). The constant term in this model is significant ($\alpha = .01$) and positive.

Table 1: Results of regression modeling: The first model (fixed-effects model)

Variable	$SP_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 OCF_{it} + \beta_2 ICF_{it} + \beta_3 FCF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$		
	Coefficients	(<i>t-static</i>)	P>Z
OCF	7.40e-09	2.80	0.006 ***
FCF	-3.71e-09	-0.99	0.325
ICF	-1.09e-08	-1.75	0.083*
_cons	2.696407	9.92	0.000***
<i>R-sq between</i>	0.2441		
<i>R-sq overall</i>	0.1327		
<i>(F-value)</i>	7.41***		

*, **, *** = p-value < .10, .05, .01 ; SP = Share Price; OCF = Operating Cash Flows; FCF = Financing Cash Flows ; ICF = Investing Cash Flows, ε = error term.

Three hypotheses are covered by this model: H₁: OCFs, H₂: FCFs, and H₃: ICFs.

The regression analysis results are discussed in this section for each variable. The first hypothesis was:

H₁: The operating cash flows (OCFs) have a statistically-significant effect on the share prices (SPs) of companies.

This study hypothesizes that there is a statistically-significant relationship between the OCFs and the SPs of companies. The results presented by Table 5.11 reveal significant, positive relationship between the OCFs and the SPs of companies ($T = 2.8$; $p = 0.006$). Therefore, the SPs will increase with the OCFs. This finding is actually consistent with the findings of many previous studies on the effect of OCFs on SPs of

firms (e.g., Quirin, O'Bryan, Wilcox & Berry (1999), Krishnan and Largay (2000), Barth et al. (2001), Al-Attar and Hussain (2004), Chotkunakitti (2005), Al-Khaddash & Al-Abbadi (2005), Farshadfar, Ng & Brimble (2008), Habib (2010), Waldron and Jordan (2010), Ebaid (2011), and Shubita (2013)), which presented empirical evidence supporting that the past OCF information can explain share prices of the companies.

H₂: The financing cash flows (FCFs) have a statistically-significant effect on the share prices (SPs) of companies.

The second hypothesis supports that there is significant relation between the FCFs and SPs of companies. The results summarized by Table 5.13 indicate a non-significant relationship between the FCFs and SPs of companies ($t = -0.99$; $p = 0.325$). This result accords with the findings of Khanji and Siam (2016).

H₃: Investing cash flows (ICF)

H₃: The investing cash flows (FCFs) have a statistically-significant effect on the share prices (SPs) of companies.

The testing results (Table 5.12) support this hypothesis and uncover that there is a significant, negative association between the SPs of companies and the ICFs ($t = -1.75$; $p = 0.083$).

6. Discussion and Conclusion

The current study found that the cash flows have significant effect on the share prices of companies. However, while the OCFs and ICFs have statistically-significant positive and negative effects, respectively, on share prices of companies, the effect of the FCFs on share prices was negative and statistically insignificant. The researcher compared this finding with findings of earlier studies. As was seen in the foregoing sub-section, the comparison resulted in categorization of the various studies into three groups; a group of similarities, a group of differences, and a group with context-specific results.

The first group of studies includes various published works with which the present study shares some results in common. First, Koerniadi and Tourani-Rad (2005) reported a significant, positive relationship between the OCFs and future stock returns of New Zealand companies during the period 1987-2003. However, they deflated all the study variables by the average total assets. Second, the present finding compares with one of the findings of Dastgir, Sajadi, and Akhgar (2009). These researchers investigated the relations between components of income statements and flow statements and the stock returns of 65 firms listed on TSEM from 2003 to 2005. One of their findings was that the cash flows from operating activities per share have significant, positive relationship with the stock returns of the sample companies. In addition, of the three cash flow categories, the ICFs explained the relatively highest percentage of variations in the stock prices (14.9%), followed by the FCFs (10.9%), and the OCFs (10.4%). Third, Mazloom, Azarberahman, and Azarberahman (2013) explored the associations of stock returns of Iranian companies in the period 2003-2011 with several cash flow and earning measures of firm's performance. Regression analysis showed that the net cash flows from operating activities ratio had a significant ($p < .05$), positive effect on the stock returns of the Iranian companies. Furthermore, of the three investigated predictors, the cash flows from the operating activities had the highest explanatory power ($R^2 = .191$) of the stock returns of the studied companies, followed by the cash flows from the investing activities ($R^2 = .060$) and the cash flows from the financing activities ($R^2 = .012$). Fourth, Novianti (2012) researched into the effects of changes in cash flows on stock returns of manufacturing companies listed on Indonesia Stock Exchange Market during the period 2008-2009. The present study shares with her study the finding that the FCFs have insignificant relationship with the share prices of the companies. Fifth, Hamza (2014) investigated the nature of the relations between the OCFs, ICFs, and FCFs, individually and combined, and stock returns of insurance companies listed on the Damascus Securities Exchange Market. This researcher found that for certain insurance companies there were significant, positive correlations between stock returns and the OCFs and negative, insignificant relations between the stock returns and the FCFs. Sixth, Olugbenga and Atanda (2014) studied the relations between financial accounting information and the market values of 57 quoted financial and non-financial companies in Nigeria in the period 1991-2010. Analysis showed that the OCFs have a significant ($p < .05$), positive effect on the share prices of the listed companies in Nigeria., and that they alone explain about 72.6% of the variations in the share prices of the sample companies. Seventh, Khanji and Siam (2015) examined the effects of cash flows on the share price of 12 Jordanian commercial

banks listed on Amman Stock Exchange Market during the period 2010-2013, taking into consideration the individual and joint effects of the OCFs, ICFs, and FCFs. Statistical analysis indicated that, similar to the findings of the present study, there is no statistically-significant ($p > .05$) effect of FCFs on the share prices of the studied Jordanian commercial banks. Eighth, Asif, Arif, and Akbar (2016) examined the relations between accounting information (EPS, capital employed per share, OCFs per share, and book value per share) and share prices of Pakistani companies listed in the KSE-30 index from 2006 to 2013. Regression modeling uncovered that the OCF per share have a significant, positive relationship with the share prices of the sample companies. Ninth, Etale and Binglar (2016) analyzed the impacts of cash flows on the stock prices in the banking sector in Nigeria during the period 2005-2014. The researchers adopted the market price per share as the proxy for stock price. Meantime, the dependent variables were the dividend to operating cash flow ratio, the cash flows to total assets ratio, and the cash flows per share ratio. Results of multiple regression analysis pointed that the three investigated cash flow components have significant, positive effects on the share prices of the 10 sample banks. These comparisons support that the findings of the present study related to the second research hypothesis (H_2) stand comparison with earlier research.

The second group of studies encircles the studies of Dastgir et al. (2009), Novianti (2012), Mazloom et al. (2013), Hamza (2014), and Khanji and Siam (2015). First, the present findings differ from results which Dastgir et al. (2009) obtained in two respects as these researchers found that cash flows from investing activities per share and cash flows from financing activities per share have significant, positive relationships with the stock returns of the sample Iranian companies. In the current study, the ICFs had a significant, negative relation with share price and the FCFs had negative, non-significant relation with share prices of the sample Jordanian companies. Second, the results of this study differ from those of Novianti (2012) in two facets owing to that this researcher found that (i) the ICFs have a significant, positive relation with the stock returns of the 64 sample manufacturing companies while the association of the stock returns of these companies with the OCFs was not significant. In the current study, the OCFs have a significant, positive relation with share prices while the ICFs had a significant, negative relation with share prices of the sample Jordanian companies. Third, the present findings differ from the results which Mazloom et al. (2013) obtained in two aspects since these researchers found that: (i) the net cash flows from investing activities ratio had significant, negative effects on the stock returns of the studied Iranian companies; and (ii) the net cash flows from financing activities ratio had significant, negative effects on the stock returns of those companies. In the present study, the ICFs had a significant, negative relation with share prices and the FCFs had negative, non-significant relation with share prices of the sample Jordanian companies. Fourth, Hamza (2014) explored the relations between the FCFs, ICFs, and OCFs and stock returns of insurance companies listed on the Damascus Securities Exchange Market. He found that for certain insurance companies there were significant positive correlations between stock returns and the ICFs while for other studied companies the relationships were non-significant. Moreover, no significant relationship between stock returns and cash flows from the three activities combined have been observed for the studied insurance companies. On the other hand, for some insurance companies there were statistically-significant, negative relations between stock returns and FCFs, while for some other companies the associations were non-significant. Fifth Khanji and Siam (2015) reported that there are no statistically-significant ($p > .05$) effects of the OCFs, ICFs, and FCFs, individually, or even combined, on the share prices of the 12 Jordanian commercial banks listed on Amman Stock Exchange Market during the period 2010-2013. The findings of the present study contradict with these findings in that in the present study (i) the cash flows combined have significant effect on the share prices, and (ii) the OCFs and ICFs individually have significant effects on the share prices of the sample Jordanian companies.

The third group of studies only includes the study of Bani Khaled (2012) who studied the effects of the cash flows on the share prices of 13 Jordanian commercial banks in the period 2000-2009. His results indicated that cash flows have a significant impact on the share prices of the studied banks and that the OCFs were the most influential variable before and after the global financial crisis. What the present study shares with that of Bani Khaled (2012) is that in both studies the OCFs were the cash flow component having the relatively highest effect on the share prices of the studied companies. Bani Khaled (2012) also reported that in the years 2007 and 2008, the share prices of the studied banks were not significantly affected by the FCFs, ICFs, or OCFs, which is a finding that this researcher related to the global financial crisis that

hit the banking sector in the world in that period and impacted the cash flows in general, thus reflecting negatively on the values of the shares in those banks.

7. References

- Al-Attar, A., & Hussain, S. (2004). Corporate data and future cash flow. *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 31(7-8), 861-903.
- Al-Khaddash, H., & Al-Abbadi, M. (2005). The relationships between each of the accounting revenue and cash flows to shareholders with equity market value of shares. *Studies: Management Sciences*, 32(1), 141-153 (In Arabic).
- Al Zararee, A., & Al-Azzawi, A. (2014). The impact of free cash flow on market value of firm. *Global Review of Accounting and Finance*, 5(2), 56 – 63.
- Asif, M., Arif, K., & Akbar, W. (2016). Impact of accounting information on share price: Empirical evidence from Pakistan stock exchange. *International Finance and Banking*, 3(1), 124-135.
- Barth, M. E., Cram, D. P., & Nelson, K. K. (2001). Accruals and the prediction of future cash flows. *The Accounting Review*, 76(1), 27-58.
- Bowen, R. M., Burgstahler, D., & Daley, L. A. (1987). The incremental information content of accrual versus cash flows. *Accounting Review*, 723-747.
- Cheng, C. S. A., & Hollie, D. (2008). Do core and non-core cash flows from operations persist differentially in predicting future cash flows? *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting*, 31, 29–53.
- Chotkunakitti, P. (2005). *Cash flows and accrual accounting in predicting future cash flow of Thai listed companies* ((Unpublished doctoral thesis). Retrieved from: epubs.scu.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1018&context=theses
- Clubb, C. D. (1995). An empirical study of the information content of accounting earnings, funds flows and cash flows in the UK. *Journal of business finance & accounting*, 22(1), 35-52.
- Dastgir, M., Sajadi, H. S., & Akhgar, O. M. (2010). The association between components of income statement, components of cash flow statement and stock returns. *Business Intelligence Journal*, 3(1), 9-21.
- Dechow, P. M., & Ge, W. (2006). The persistence of earnings and cash flows and the role of special items: Implications for the accrual anomaly. *Review of Accounting Studies*, 11(2), 253-296.
- Ebaid, I. E. (2011). Accruals and the prediction of future cash flows: Empirical evidence from an emerging market. *Management Research Review*, 34(7), 1-32.
- Etale, L. M., & Bingilar, P. F. (2016). The impact of cash flow on stock price in the banking sector of Nigeria. *Business, Management and Economics Research*, 2(7), 136-140.
- Farshadfar, S., Ng, C., & Brimble, M. (2008). The relative ability of earnings and cash flow data in forecasting future cash flows: Some Australian evidence. *Pacific Accounting Review*, 20(3), 254-268.
- Habib, A. (2010). Prediction of operating cash flows: Further evidence from Australia. *Australian Accounting Review*, 20(2), 134.

- Hadi, J., Bashir, O., Abolfazl, G. M., & Maryam, M. (2013). The relationship between free cash flows, accruals, and firm value. *World of Sciences Journal*, 1(12), 26-33.
- Hamza, m. (2014). the relationship between informational content of cash flows statement and stock returns from accounting perspective of IAS (7)(an empirical study). *European journal of accounting auditing and finance research*, 2(10), 67-84.
- Khanji, I. M., and Siam, A. Z. (2015). The effect of cash flow on share price of the Jordanian commercial banks listed in Amman Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 7(5), 109-115.
- Koerniadi, H., & Tourani-Rad, A. (2005). *Accruals and cash flows anomalies: Evidence from the New Zealand stock market* (Auckland University of Technology, Research Paper Series, Paper 24-2005). Retrieved from: https://www.aut.ac.nz/__data/assets/pdf_file/0007/48481/enterprise_and_innovation_24-2005.pdf
- Krishnan, G. V., & Largay, J. A. (2000). The predictive ability of direct method cash flow information. *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 27(1-2), 215-245.
- Lees, A. T., & Leibman, P. R. (2000). Free cash flow: back to basics. *Oil & Gas Investor*, 20(4), 67-70.
- Mazloom, A., Azarberahman, A., & Azarberahman, J. (2013). The association between various earnings and cash flow measures of firm performance and stock returns: Some Iranian evidence. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, 3(1), 24-41.
- Mundia, W. I. (2016). *Relationship between Free Cash Flows and Stock Prices of Non Financial Firms Listed at the Nairobi Securities Exchange* (Unpublished master's thesis). Retrieved from: erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/99971
- Novianti, D. (2012). The influence of cash flow changing and profit accounting to stock return in manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia stock exchange. *Proceedings of the 13th Malaysia Indonesia Conference on Economics, Management and Accounting*. Retrieved from: http://eprints.unsri.ac.id/3206/1/the_influence_of_cash_flow_changing_and_profit_accounting.pdf
- Olugbenga, A. A., & Atanda, O. A. (2014). The relationship between financial accounting information and market values of quoted firms in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Contemporary Research in Accounting, Auditing and Business Ethics* (GJCRA), 1(1), 22-39.
- Quirin, J. J., O'Bryan, D., Wilcox, W. E., & Berry, K. T. (1999). Forecasting cash flow from operations: additional evidence. *The Mid-Atlantic Journal of Business*, 35(2-3), 135-42.
- Richardson, S., Sloan, R. G., Soliman, M., & Tuna, I. (2001). Information in accruals about the quality of earnings.
- Shubita, M. F. (2013). Accruals and cash flows: A case of Jordan. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 5(3), 428-441.
- Waldron, M. A., & Jordan, C. E. (2010). The comparative predictive abilities of accrual earnings and cash flows in periods of economic turbulence: the case of the IT bubble. *The Journal of Applied Business Research*, 26(1), 85-97.